

The Special Financial Crisis: How Students With Learning Disabilities Can Be Financially Literate With The Implementation Of Interactive Animation

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ABSTRACT

Financial literacy among Generation Z students has declined over the last few years, and students with learning disabilities are especially susceptible to this problem. These groups of students struggle with basic financial literacy, leading to negative consequences for their future economic stability. The current financial literacy programs aren't adjusted enough to their abilities, putting them in a more difficult position to achieve more financial knowledge. This research aims to consolidate interactive animation as an effective teaching aid to address this issue. Interactive animation, which utilizes visual, auditory, and kinesthetic learning modes, can easily explain complex financial concepts to special needs students with a higher level of engagement. The proposed approach aims to increase understanding and retention by making the learning process more effective and interesting for students. With early exposure to the fundamental aspects of financial literacy, these students are better equipped for the long term through enhanced financial decision-making ability and overall financial planning. The study outlines the application of a personalized education method to support those with special needs, providing a solution to enhance inclusion and decrease the financial literacy gap. It ultimately promotes the use of interactive animation in special education systems and how it can facilitate an effective transition into a successful financial future.

Keywords: *Financial Literacy, Special Needs Students, Interactive Animation, Learning Disabilities, Personalized Education, Financial Decision-Making*

1. INTRODUCTION

The lack of financial literacy is a problem that continues to persist in today's society as financial literacy rates continue to decrease. Out of all living generations, Generation Z (those born from 1995-2010) has the highest amount of financial illiteracy and statistically among the highest

levels of student loan debt, consolidating their illiteracy and contributing to poor financial decisions and economic instability as a generation (Francis & Hoefel, 2018; Yakoboski et al., 2024). This is a growing issue that needs to be addressed or else it will continue to get worse throughout younger generations, ultimately leading to severe financial losses in the future. Special needs students are especially vulnerable as it is harder for them to learn and grow knowledge compared to the average individual (Grigorenko et al., 2021). Their attention rates and ability to learn are much slower, which means not exposing them to basic financial knowledge early on can cause a vast delay in their literacy, inhibiting their ability to become more independent in the future. Current financial literacy topics are too complex, and the basics of financial literacy need to be addressed (Henning & Johnston-Rodriguez, 2018). They also need to adapt to these students' needs properly, resulting in a lack of learning and comprehension of the knowledge given. To solve this problem, interactive animation can be used as a tool to ease their transition into more complex financial topics and ultimately integrate them into society. Learning is done mainly through three types of styles, which are visual, auditory, and kinesthetic learning. Interactive animation can address all of these learning styles, with the visuals allowing the graphic focus of information, the verbal auditory information allowing for an emphasis on financial terminology, and the kinesthetic interactive features allowing for increased hands-on involvement. This will ultimately help those with special needs to retain and understand the given knowledge (Baglama et al., 2018). Addressing the societal gap in teaching basic financial knowledge to these students will give them a sense of autonomy and confidence, resulting in their future financial success.

2. DISCUSSION

2.1 GEN Z'S Rates Of Financial Instability

The lack of financial literacy has been a growing concern worldwide and has become increasingly prevalent in recent years. According to the TIAA Institute-GFLEC Personal Finance Index, a survey was taken each year from 2017-2024 in which U.S. individuals assessed their knowledge of basic financial topics. The survey results indicated that the average percentage of questions answered correctly had consistently been decreasing since 2020, from over half in 2020 to a slightly better 48% in 2024. This number, although low across generations, was considerably the lowest in Generation Z at a mere 37% of index questions answered correctly in

2024 (Yakoboski et al., 2024). The Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis states that on average, Generation Z had over \$20,000 in student loan debt, which was recorded to be 13% more than that of millennials. This disparity was also seen in the median value of Generation Z’s loan value standing at over \$12,500, 14% more than millennials (Kent & Ricketts, 2022).

Figure 1: Average & Median Student Loan Debts for Generation Z in 2022 vs. Millennials in 2006 [Adjusted for Inflation] (Kent & Ricketts, 2022)

As the current youngest generation of adults capable of sustaining themselves economically, Generation Z’s poor financial knowledge compared to older generations outlines the severity of the financial literacy crisis that progressively continues to persist in today’s world, especially affecting those with special needs.

2.2 Financial Challenges Faced By Individuals With Disabilities

Individuals with learning disabilities currently face numerous financial challenges that affect their everyday lives and ability to implement their financial knowledge. According to the National Disability Institute, in 2023, a mere 40% of those with disabilities who were of working age were employed, which was significantly lower than that of those without disabilities. The

significantly low percentage ultimately leads to almost half of those with disabilities who can work having household incomes less than \$30,000 as opposed to those without disabilities standing at a mere 21% (Warren et al., 2023). This shows how financially unhealthy those with disabilities are in comparison to the general population. These financial crises are aggravated by the hurdles to effective financial education as well as financial inclusion. It is much more difficult for those with learning disabilities to become financially independent as they suffer from proper financial knowledge, which ultimately results in a negative effect on their daily life in which they are met with numerous financial decisions to make.

2.3 Difficulties Faced By Special Needs Students

Students with special needs face conditions that affect their cognitive abilities to address certain tasks that they must complete that are either inhibited or slower than that of an average individual.

Figure 2: Academic Difficulty Experience Comparison of Students With and Without Disabilities: United States Elementary & Secondary Education Students, 2016 (Zill, 2023)

The graphic above portrays how students with learning disabilities have significantly higher academic difficulty experiences than those of regular students, having over twice as many difficulties in all categories recorded. The disparities in difficulties were most prevalent in the “Student Suspended” and “Student Repeated Grade” categories, with over 3 times as many students with learning disabilities suffering.

According to Grigorenko and colleagues, students with learning disabilities can receive a wide range of conditions associated with their disability, such as having difficulties in learning certain academic concepts or experiencing developmental disorders inhibiting their ability to pay attention. Their conditions result in long-term harmful learning deficiencies due to functional social and behavioral difficulties (Grigorenko et al., 2021). Neurodevelopmental disorders had a high frequency of specific subject disorders, with reading and math disorders being seen commonly among young children. The coexistence of both reading and math disorders in children with disabilities is especially concerning, standing as high as having a 45% chance of occurrence. These disorders can have a significantly negative impact on academic and career success (Moll et al., 2018). Working memory is defined as the ability to retain given information in a short period and carry out a task based on that information. Working memory is also affected directly by the neurological disorders exhibited by those with learning disabilities (Cowan, 2013). In 2015, Peng and colleagues conducted a meta-analysis exploring the relationship between working memory and mathematics. They found that there was a correlation coefficient greater than 0.3 in the 95% confidence interval, signifying a medium positive correlation between mathematics ability and working memory (Peng et al., 2015). A medium positive correlation was also mirrored in another study conducted by Peng and colleagues in 2018, where a correlation coefficient of approximately 0.3 was inhibited in the relation between working memory and reading (Peng et al., 2017).

Figures 3 (Reading) & 4 (Mathematics): Assessment Score Growth in Reading & Mathematics Proficiency Comparison of Students With and Without Disabilities: United States, 4th to 12th grade, 2011-2019 (Zill, 2023)

The graphs above depict that although there is growth in both students with and without disabilities in reading and mathematics, the achievement gap between both groups widened in each subject area. This was especially evident in mathematics, where the assessment scores of non-disabled students had increased by 43 points from 2011 to 2015 as opposed to disabled students, whose scores had raised a mere 29 points, expanding the achievement gap between the groups from 11 to over 14 percent. These results highlight how disorders in those with learning disabilities lead to greater difficulties in learning new information than that of a regular student learning the same given information. Without possessing the proper financial knowledge to make decisions, special needs students are much more confused about where to put their money and how to use it.

2.4 Special Needs Students Versus Average Individuals

We can see that students with special needs students are more financially unstable than the average individual.

Disability Status	Student Loan Default Rate
No Disability	28%
Disability	35%
➤ Emotional/Psychiatric Disability	60%

➤ Mobility/Orthopedic Impairment	40%
➤ Health Impairment	37%
➤ Attention Deficit Disorder	25%
➤ Depression	23%
➤ Other Disability	40%

Figure 5: Student Loan Default Rate After 12-year Repayment Period of Students With and Without Disabilities in 2003-2004 (Campbell, 2018)

The table above demonstrates that students without disabilities have a loan default rate of 28%, however, this percentage is much higher for those with disabilities, standing at a staggering 35%. Those with disabilities are especially affected in the “Emotional or Psychiatric Condition” category, with over half of them defaulting on their loans within the 12-year repayment period. This outlines that those with cognitive impairments are the most affected group in high default rates out of other categorized disabilities.

It can also be seen that the decisions that students with learning disabilities make are more irrational than those of an average individual. Those with learning disabilities display irrational decision-making behaviors in places where they must use high-level cognitive thinking. This mainly occurs due to difficulties in executive functions, emotional regulation, and cognitive processing (Grigorenko et al., 2021). These students are more likely to act impulsively and are less efficient in solving problems, resulting in them making unsuitable financial and personal decisions for their current and future lives. For them to make more reasonable decisions, they need to be more knowledgeable of what decisions to make and at what time. Improving their knowledge of financial literacy can be a principal factor in their future monetary success.

2.5 Current Financial Literacy Curriculum For Special Needs Students

The current financial literacy curriculum that is implemented to educate students with and without special needs about financial literacy contains numerous limitations in the educational knowledge provided. Financial literacy education curricula measuring the financial capability of students have had false presuppositions that the same conditions define everyone, regardless of whether they are regular students or students with special needs (Henning & Johnston-Rodriguez, 2018). The assumption that all students go through the same process of

being able to learn is misleading as there are countless differences in situations and circumstances between the two groups of students, especially concerning financial literacy. Those with learning disabilities should be taught with accommodations to adjust for their disadvantages and for them to learn the information effectively.

There is also a lack of effective financial literacy programs for individuals with disabilities to teach basic self-determination skills. It is much harder for individuals with disabilities to attain the necessary knowledge and skills needed to make the right financial decisions to lead an independent life. The lack of education programs directly results in a significant decrease in their ability to take up employment in a competitive environment, resulting in them having limited access to increase their financial potential overall (Caniglia & Michali, 2018). This issue is exacerbated by the curricula not being developed enough, so people with disabilities have no guiding structure to facilitate their way in their everyday finances. Therefore, they often find themselves at a disadvantage when it comes to making educated financial choices, which jeopardizes their long-term stability and general financial well-being.

This issue can be addressed through new, innovative financial literacy curricula tailored specifically to their style of learning and ability to retain the information at hand.

2.6 Importance of Financial Literacy For Special Needs Students

Financial literacy proves to directly correlate with having a better capability in order to make better financial decisions. Those who have an adequate level of financial literacy are more equipped with their ability to comprehend economic processes and bounce back after potential financial losses. With greater financial knowledge, people have enhanced skills to deal with difficult monetary situations and take advantage of the best opportunities to improve their overall quality of life. Financial literacy also allows for a positive effect on cognitive processes, including behavioral effects such as regulating one's emotions or being more organized with one's everyday life (Bai & Khan, 2023). According to the National Financial Educators Council (2023), Americans were found to have lost over \$1,500 on average annually due to their financial illiteracy. These losses were a result of ignorance in handling credit, budget, and risk assessment. One of the most prevalent areas where such losses were evident was credit card interest and fees, where individuals were uninformed of how interest accrued over time and ended up accumulating significantly higher amounts of debt. Another key factor was

overspending, as people with poor financial literacy had difficulties figuring out their budget and taking multiple constituents into account, including their net income and discretionary expenses. Furthermore, improperly managing loans and falling victim to fraudulent transactions leads to an increased level of financial pressure. Overall, being more knowledgeable about where money is going and how it works allows one to gain a better understanding of how to make critical decisions at hand.

Financial literacy not only helps people in the short term but also impacts their lives in the long term. A report conducted by The Financial Industry Regulatory Authority described how financially wise consumers were able to handle finances more accurately. They were considered to be significantly more likely to avoid debt accumulation by making sure their spending did not exceed their income, having three months' worth of money saved up in their emergency fund, and owning at least one type of retirement account (Henderson, 2024). These characteristics exemplified their financial cushion for increased economic stability both in the short and long term. Financial literacy can ultimately result in the benefit of these special needs students because it will allow them to have a better base and make well-educated decisions for themselves and their future.

2.7 The Role of Interactive Animation In Financial Education

Interactive animation can be used as an educational tool to address the current crisis of special needs students being financially illiterate to make better decisions. A major advantage of using animation is that it is possible to explain information in a manner more comprehensible than when teaching with solely textual information. For students with disabilities, learning through conventional means is often difficult, especially when it comes to abstract concepts or ideas. When such ideas are presented with the use of animation, the given material is easier for students to grasp with the depictive relationships between different ideas being vividly portrayed. This allows for a longer overall retention time for the students learning the information at hand, leading to a more successful learning experience. Furthermore, animation acknowledges the developmental and cognitive differences present between special needs students learning the same information. According to Mulholland et. al. in an experiment testing the ability of special needs students to learn through animation, an animated software called Team Up With Timo was implemented to teach language skills to children with speech and language disabilities. It was

discovered that the implementation of the software benefitted over 75% of the students, with 60% of the students scoring near-perfect scores on a subsequent vocabulary test (Mulholland et al., 2008). Students also benefit from increased participation in the learning process. When students resonate with the characters in animated stories or situations, their emotional reflection will promote a deeper consolidation of memory of the concepts (Baglama et al., 2018). This allows for the further development of skills in areas applicable to the real world, such as better problem-solving skills and enhanced motor coordination. This approach to knowledge makes the process enjoyable and less stressful as opposed to more formal learning methods and, therefore, beneficial for learners with special needs. Animation as a distinct medium of instruction is very effective for improving retention and enhancing understanding as a whole.

2.8 Implementation of Interactive Animation For Financial Literacy

Interactive animation can be designed in such a way that addresses the key aspects of special needs students for them to be financially literate in the best manner possible. Animation should convey ideas so that special needs students with no prior knowledge can understand the information. The best way this could be advanced is through the catering of the principal learning styles: visual, auditory, and kinesthetic. According to Oliveira et. al. (2023), adapting an educational course to one's learning style allows for one to succeed in the best possible way. Their quantitative study implemented the use of the chi-square test for learners adapted to a specific learning style, to which an odds ratio analysis found that these students were 3.33 times more likely to pass the course than those who did not exhibit performance with a specific learning style (Oliveira et al., 2023). Animation addresses the preferred style of visual learners in which the visuals provided allow them to gain an in-depth understanding at a much better rate. It can be designed using colorful graphics and diagrams for key concepts to be addressed in the best manner. Visuals via the color, contrast, background, and design of the animation could enhance the information, along with consistency through a seamless flow and logical organization. Animation can incorporate verbal information provided by a speaker, which takes into account the adapted preferred style of auditory learning. Making animation interactive will consider kinesthetic hands-on learning, in which special needs students will be engaged and actively involved in their learning to gain insight into the concepts at hand. Interactive animation addresses each of the three unique learning styles of special needs students, contributing to an

improved learning experience, higher information retention rate, and smoother integration into society.

The animation can be integrated into a website with accompanying assignments that reinforce the information students have learned through the animation, with the website being offered as a resource for integration into the special education curriculum for schools. Students can complete assignments on the website and take exams that assess their knowledge, with special education teachers adjusting specific concepts to provide the students based on personal experience. The financial literacy curriculum can be effectively integrated into the special needs curriculum with the combination of a website and hands-on resources that teachers can offer students, such as paper money or other tangible assistive tools. The basic knowledge that special needs students have already acquired from the standard educational special needs curriculum such as basic math concepts can be directly applied to the financial knowledge being taught over time. The information given can be adjusted until the students have met the standard of possessing basic financial literacy through examinations on the website or teacher assessments of students' knowledge.

3. CONCLUSION

Integrating a program for special needs financial education into schools will provide a strong foundation for more complex monetary concepts that special education students will gain over time. It will also provide long-term benefits of being knowledgeable when those with special needs earn money and need to make decisions at critical times, such as where to invest their money and when to take a loan. Despite the emphasis placed on financial education with an increasing number of states adopting financial literacy curriculum into their schools, there is a lack of emphasis on inclusivity pertaining to special needs students. It is essential that special needs students gain the same knowledge to apply in a real-world setting in the future. Advocacy for their curriculum and integration into schools along with the specific developments of financial literacy programs can help alleviate this educational disparity.

4. LIMITATIONS

The goal of this study is to prove the effectiveness of interactive animation as an implementation for financial literacy in special needs curriculum, however, there haven't currently been any real-world implementations that have proven successful. The study reinforces the need for this gap to be addressed but cannot demonstrate how well initiatives or projects can be implemented or how effective they will be.

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REFERENCES

1. Baglama, B., Yucesoy, Y., & Yikmis, A. (2018, August 27). *Using Animation as a Means of Enhancing Learning of Individuals with Special Needs*. TEM Journal. https://www.temjournal.com/content/73/TemJournalAugust2018_670_677.pdf
2. Bai, R., & Khan, W. (2023, November 14). *Impact of financial literacy, mental budgeting and self control on financial wellbeing: Mediating impact of investment decision making*. NCBI. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC10645357/>
3. Campbell, C. (2018, October 16). *The Forgotten Faces of Student Loan Default*. Center for American Progress. <https://www.americanprogress.org/article/forgotten-faces-student-loan-default/>

4. Caniglia, J., & Michali, Y. (2018). *A Financial Literacy Course for Postsecondary Students with Intellectual Disabilities*. Journal of Postsecondary Education and Disability. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1200606.pdf>
5. Cowan, N. (2013, December 3). *Working Memory Underpins Cognitive Development, Learning, and Education*. National Library of Medicine. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4207727/>
6. Francis, T., & Hoefel, F. (2018, November 18). *'True Gen': Generation Z and its implications for companies*. McKinsey & Company. <https://www.drthomaswu.com/uicmpaccsmac/Gen%20Z.pdf>
7. Grigorenko, E. L., Compton, D., Fuchs, L., Wagner, R., Willcutt, E., & Fletcher, J. M. (2021, January 1). *Understanding, Educating, and Supporting Children with Specific Learning Disabilities: 50 Years of Science and Practice*. National Library of Medicine. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6851403/>
8. Henderson, R. (2024, August 9). *Financial Literacy Statistics*. MarketWatch. <https://www.marketwatch.com/guides/banking/financial-literacy-statistics/>
9. Henning, M. B., & Johnston-Rodriguez, S. (2018, July 30). *Evaluating financial literacy curriculum for young adults with special needs: A review of content, universal design for learning, and culturally responsive curriculum principles*. SageJournals. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/2047173418789593>
10. Kent, A. H., & Ricketts, L. R. (2022, August 25). *How Does Gen Z Student Debt Compare with Millennials?* Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis. <https://www.stlouisfed.org/on-the-economy/2022/aug/how-does-gen-z-student-debt-compare-millennials>

11. Moll, K., Landerl, K., Snowling, M. J., & Schulte-Körne, G. (2018, August 25). *Understanding comorbidity of learning disorders: task-dependent estimates of prevalence*. National Library of Medicine. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30144072/>
12. Mulholland, R., Pete, A. M., & Popeson, J. (2008, July). *Using Animated Language Software with Children Diagnosed with Autism Spectrum Disorders*. TEACHING Exceptional Children Plus. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ967725.pdf>
13. National Financial Educators Council. (2024, March 28). *Financial Illiteracy Costs: Survey, Causes, Consequences | NFEC*. National Financial Educators Council. <https://www.financialeducatorsCouncil.org/financial-illiteracy-costs/>
14. Oliveira, A., Spinola, V., Garrido, D., Teixeira, M. M., Salles, C., & Haddad, A. E. (2023, July 27). *Influence of learning styles on student performance in self-instructional courses*. National Library of Medicine. Retrieved September 14, 2024, from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC10374043/>
15. Peng, P., Barnes, M., Wang, C., Wang, W., Li, S., Swanson, H. L., Dardick, W., & Tao, S. (2017, October 30). *A meta-analysis on the relation between reading and working memory*. National Library of Medicine. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/29083201/>
16. Peng, P., Namkung, J., Barnes, M., & Sun, C. (2015). *A meta-analysis of mathematics and working memory: Moderating effects of working memory domain, type of mathematics skill, and sample characteristics*. APA PsycNet. <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/2015-41049-001?doi=1>
17. Warren, A., Chege, W., Greene, M., & Berdie, L. (2023, August). *The Financial Health of People With Disabilities*. Financial Health Network.

<https://www.nationaldisabilityinstitute.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/09/the-financial-health-of-people-with-disabilities-report-final-0923.pdf>

18. Yakoboski, P. J., Lusardi, A., & Sticha, A. (2024). *New insights for improving financial well-being*. Global Financial Literacy Excellence Center (GFLEC). https://gflec.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/TIAA_GFLEC_Report_PFin_April2024_07.pdf

19. Zill, N. (2023, March 30). *The Disability Dilemma*. Institute for Family Studies. <https://ifstudies.org/blog/the-disability-dilemma>